

Microfinance an Opportunity through SHG's Economic Status - An Impact study

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Received : 05/04/2023

1st BPR : 20/04/2023

2nd BPR : 29/04/2023

Accepted : 11/05/2023

Abstract

Microfinance can be termed as small scale provision of financial services like credit, savings, insurance, money transfer and counselling to people who are unable to obtain these services from the formal financial institutions. There is one of the major tool used for microfinance is Shelf help groups (SHG's). SHG is the small autonomous groups of people living in the vicinity who voluntary associate themselves for common concern, mainly to eradicate poverty. It is a group of approximate 10-20 members who need not necessarily be registered. All the members agree for common savings, generate a common fund and utilises the same for their credit need through a management. This study is mainly an impact in which I had find out the impact on income level of beneficiaries by this scheme of SHG. The data has been collected through primary sources for analysis purpose and secondary data also used for its introduction and for the review of literature related to this paper. The data of income related factors has been divided between before and after the scheme of SHG's and this data is analysed by using Paired-T test. The result found through analyses showing positive impact on the income of members of SHG's.

Key words: Microfinance, SHG's, Members, Impact and Income.

INTRODUCTION

Microfinance has emerged as an important tool of financial inclusion for India's poor millions left out of the formal banking systems for providing resources for creating productive assets to raise their living standards.

According to International Labor Organization (ILO) 21, "Microfinance is an economic development approach that involves providing financial services through institutions to low income clients".

Chittagong University (Bangladesh) economics professor is better known as the man, who won the Nobel Peace Prize in 2006 for his thirty three years old dream venture - Grameen Bank. He is Muhammad Yunus who is known as the father of Micro - credit and a staunch believer in the principle of the 'social business enterprise'. He initially lent \$ 27 to few poor farmers in 1976, and today, his brainchild Grameen bank has 2,422 branches with aggregate loans of more than \$ 6.8 billion (lent to more than 7.4 million people).

With a modest beginning in the 1980s microfinance today has emerged as one of the most potent tools for poverty elimination, economic empowerment, gender inequality and financial inclusion of a large number of poor and marginalised sections of the society. Started with small efforts at forming informal Self-Help Groups (SHGs) of the poor to provide much needed access to credit and saving facilities, the microfinance sector has grown significantly in the past two decades, both in terms of number of people covered and nature of services offered to the rural poor. Microfinance today is considered to be uniquely placed to take over the challenge of poverty elimination across the world due to better understanding of problems faced by the rural people, greater accessibility among the poor and flexibility in operations.

Microfinance can be termed as small scale provision of financial services like credit, savings, insurance, money transfer and counselling to people who are unable to obtain these services from the formal financial institutions. They are generally left out of the formal commercial credit system for the reason that they have no formal employment and collateral securities to offer against the loans from the banking system and banks have to incur large transactions and monitoring costs in serving small credit needs of these poor buyers.

SHG is the small autonomous groups of people living in the vicinity who voluntarily associate themselves for common concern, mainly to eradicate poverty. It is a group of approximate 10-20 members who need not necessarily be registered. All the members agree for common savings, generate a common fund and utilise the same for their credit need through a management.

“Saving for – credit later” should be the motto of every SHG so that the main function is to encourage the habit of regular and continuous saving among members, the amount may be small.

The saving then can be used as loan for members and the purpose, amount, rate of interest etc. of the loan is decided by the SHGs by preparing proper accounts. SHGs may open a saving bank account on the name of SHGs with bank to enable SHG members to obtain loans from banks and repaying the same.

SHGs meet on regular basis to discuss and to find solution to problems faced by the members of the group.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Economic condition is measured through level of saving, income, standard of living, employment, and number of assets holding such as machineries, equipment and houses owned and there is a very important relation between micro finance which is stated below:-

Archana Sinha (2004) has concluded in her paper work that the understanding of the viability of micro finance requires a detailed and comprehensive analysis from the right perspective. Micro finance can contribute to solving the problem of inadequate housing both in urban and rural areas and other urban services as an integral part of poverty eradication programmes. The challenges behind it lies in finding the level of easiness and flexibility in the access of credit instrument that could make it match the multiple requirements of credit for the low-income borrowers without imposing high amount of cost of monitoring its end use upon the supplier of micro credit. According to her a promising solution is to provide multipurpose loans or composite credit for income generation, employment generation, housing improvement and consumption support.

Makandar and Mulla (2013) has stated in his study that micro finance not only bring financial empowerment but also create the structure for inclusive growth of the society. The study resulted that the income of 75% of sampled members of Self help groups increased and 90% of them changed their pattern of saving and started depositing into bank account and post offices and majority 53% members started saving Rs.3, 000 P.M and along with these changes their self confidence also increased and also able to get more basic amenities.

Center for microfinance (2006) has stated in this study that microfinance is an effective instrument to deals with the prevailing situation of poverty and the Self help groups are working a charismatic activities in order to alleviate the poverty in Rajasthan. The study concluded that availability of funds is not a cause of problem but the accessibility of funds is considered a bottleneck in the path of getting the financial services to the rural poor.

Murty, Pandu and Subrahmaniam (2014) has stated in their research work, titled “The Need for Socio-Economic Financial Support & its Impact on Economic Development: A Critical Analysis” that microfinance has the positive impact on the per capita income, saving, children schooling and on the net worth of the member of microfinance scheme and it also have shown better result at village level in terms of employment, income, education and fertility on all the villagers.

Elizabeth, Jonathan and Sayed (2003) has described in their study entitled, "Is microfinance an effective strategy to reach the millennium development goals" that microfinance is assisting the poor ones by increasing their available sources of income in order to draw out them from the cycle of poverty and its sever consequence hunger among them. Through microfinance the poor become able to avail the micro loan which pushes them towards the situation in which they can avail business opportunities, able to pay the fees of school and hitherto them came out of the vicious circle of poverty. It is analysed in the study that microfinance also assist them to meet their consumption needs, the need of fund arises at the time natural calamities or the untimely death of the earner of the family and without microfinance they move into situation of vulnerability on the happening of all these uncertainties. They able to get out of the situation of destitute when they accumulate their small saving and open a saving account and then able to acquire the assets to make their future secure.

S. Subramanian (2010) has stated in his study about the role of microfinance in the economic situation of members. It is analysed in the study that the respondents average amount of saving increased between Rs. 3,000 and 6,000 by 9.65% more in the post-period of joining the group as compared to before joining period, 78.9% respondents were able to borrow more than Rs. 20,000 after joining the group as compared to no borrowing of this amount in pre-joining period, 56.96% respondents were investing this credit into productive activities and remaining in consumption activities in their post joining period, 72.3% respondents have acquired the assets above the worth of Rs. 4,000 in their post joining period, 94% of them agreed that after joining the group their assets holding increased, 40% of them started earning more than Rs. 37,500 P.A average income after joining group

Milford Bateman (2011) has stated in the study titled "Microfinance as a development and poverty reduction policy: is it everything it's cracked up to be?" that microfinance has significant impact on povert reduction by taking into consideration the public debts and the penetration and expention of investment and which ultimately brings and promote the growth and development of a nation.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study is to find out the impact SHG's on the economic status of its member.

HYPOTHESIS OF THE STUDY

The null hypotheses is framed for achieving the objective stated above. The main hypotheses is as follows:-

HO = There is no significant impact of microfinance through SHG's on economic and financial condition of members (beneficiaries).

Sub-Hypothesis for economic status variables are framed as given below:-

HO (a) = There is no significant difference in level of income of members before and after joining self help group.

HO (b) = There is no significant difference on amount and product of expenditure of member before and after joining self help group.

HO (c) = There is no significant difference in amount of saving before and after joining self help group.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

All the six blocks of Uttarkashi district has been selected for in depth analysis of the study such as Purola, Nawgaon, Dunda, Bhatwari, Chinyalisaur and Mori in Uttarkashi district of Uttarakhand.

The 20 villages from each block have been taken for study in which at least two SHGs has formed and working through the Swaran Jayanti Gramin Swarojgar Yojana (SGSY) and having bank linkages.

ANALYSES OF DATA

The economic impact of microfinance through SHGs is analysed in detail by considering the many aspects of economic factors such as the average annual income of the members before and after

joining SHGs, average annual expenditure incurred by members before and after joining SHGs, average annual saving of members before and after joining SHGs and all these aspects has been analysed through Paired T-Test and all these aspects are explained in detail below:-

1 (a) AVERAGE ANNUAL INCOME OF MEMBERS FROM DIFFERENT SOURCES

The different main sources of income is used on the basis of pilot study conducted earlier to have some idea about the different sources of income received by members in the situation of before joining SHGs and after joining SHGs. Therefore the different sources of income selected were income from agriculture, income from diary, and income from petty businesses and also include income from any other source. The level of income of members assists them to enhance their economic status.

Table - 1 (a)

Average annual income distribution

Sr. No.	SOURCES OF INCOME	Before joining SHG (₹)	After joining SHG (₹)
1.	From Agriculture	9164	16254.21
2.	From Dairying	3594.58	14204.42
3.	Petty business	128	4854
4.	Any other	1497.33	2112.25
TOTAL		14383.91	37424.88

Source: - Data collected from primary source

This table states about the different sources of income for the selected members of SHGs before and after joining SHGs. The average annual total income of members before joining SHGs was ₹14,383.91 and which increased up to ₹ 37424.88 after joining the SHGs and all the sources of income has increased but the maximum contribution in this increase was the increase in the average annual amount from petty business is found.

Paired T-Test for different sources of income

For the purpose to know the significant difference of income in before and after joining SHGs by the members the null hypothesis is framed and which states that "There is no significant difference in level of income of members before and after joining self help group" and it is analysed through the use of Paired T-Test.

The result found by applying Paired T-Test is given in Table- below:-

Table - 1 (a)-I

Result of Paired T-Test for different sources of income

Sr. No.	Measures of income	Calculated value of Paired T-Test	Level of significance	Result
1.	Agriculture	-21.880	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
2.	Dairying	-18.512	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
3.	Petty business	-9.893	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
4.	Any other	-5.067	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level

It is revealed from the table-6.18 that all the different sources of income showing a significant difference in the income of members before and after joining the SHGs as the level of significance is

0.000 which is less than alpha values 0.01 and 0.05 therefore the null hypothesis is rejected for all the different sources of income.

5.2.2 AVERAGE ANNUAL EXPENDITURE INCURRED BY MEMBERS ON DIFFERENT ACTIVITIES

The average level of annual expenditure incurred by members has also taken into consideration for the purpose to analyse the economic condition of members before and after joining SHGs. The distribution of expenditure incurred is sub-divided among number of main activities such as expenditure on food, expenditure on education of children, expenditure on health, expenditure on festivals celebrated by members, expenditure incurred on animal rearing (for their fodder & medical etc.) and expenditure incurred on any other activities such as clothing etc.

Table - 6.19
Average annual expenditure distribution

Sr. No.	Items	Before joining SHG (₹)	After joining SHG (₹)
1.	Expenditure on food	4575.13	4898.68
2.	Expenditure on education	3500.32	6272.65
3.	Expenditure on health	1389.95	1823.38
4.	Expenditure on festivals	340.25	517.83
5.	Expenditure on animal rearing	933.25	2929.28
6.	Expenditure on other items	2388.3	2965.75
	TOTAL	13127.2	19407.57

Source: - Data collected from primary source

The table - 6.19 given above describing the expenditure incurred by members on different activities before joining SHGs and after joining SHGs. The expenditure on all the activities has increased but the major increase has seen in the expenditure incurred on education which is from ₹ 3500.32 to ₹ 6272.65 which revealed that the members were becoming financially more capable to provide better education to their children and good amount of increase also found in the expenditure on animal rearing which is from ₹ 933.25 to ₹ 2929.28 which proof that the more of the income has generated through animals (diary) therefore more of the expenditure the members has incurred on animal rearing. The meager amount of increase has shown in the food expenditure, health related expenditure, festival expenditure and on any other expenditure.

Paired T-Test for different activities of expenditures

For the purpose to know the significant difference of expenditure in before and after joining SHGs by the members the null hypothesis is framed and which states that "There is no significant difference on amount of expenditure of member before and after joining group" and it is analysed through the use of Paired T-Test.

The result found by applying Paired T-Test is given in Table-6.20 below:-

Table - 6.20
Result of Paired T-Test for different activities of expenditure

Sr. No.	Measures of expenditure	Calculated value of Paired T-Test	Level of Significance	Result
1.	Food	-2.274	0.024	Insignificant at 1% and 5% level
2.	Education	-8.062	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
3.	Health	-14.861	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
4.	Festival	-4.421	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
5.	Animal	-18.772	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
6.	Any other	-19.801	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level

It is evident from the table-6.20 that the null hypothesis is rejected for all the different activities of expenditure except the expenditure incurred on food items and therefore all the different activities of expenditure except food items showing a significant difference in the expenditure of members before and after joining the SHGs on all the different level of significance as the value arrived is 0.000 which are less than 0.05 and 0.01 but on food expenditure the difference is insignificant result in before and after joining SHGs at 1% and 5% level of significance because the value is 0.024 which is more than 0.01 and 0.05.

5.2.3 AVERAGE ANNUAL SAVING BY MEMBERS IN DIFFERENT AGENCIES

The saving is considered as the backbone of SHG scheme of microfinance so that this collective saving of all the members is channelised into productive sector. The saving is the source for the planning of the investment and the expenditure 7.

The members has saved into number of saving agencies before and after joining SHGs such as in post office, in banks, with friends, with SHGs itself. The information related to average annual amount of saving under different saving agencies by the members is given below in table 6.21:-

Table - 6.21
Average annual saving distribution among different agencies

Sr. No	Name of Agency	Before joining SHG (₹)	After joining SHG (₹)
1.	Post office saving	308.5	212.75
2.	Bank saving	778.5	1047.792
3.	Saving with friends	193.67	105.5
4.	saving with SHG	0	358
	TOTAL	1280.67	1724.042

Source: - Data collected from primary source

It is evident from the data given in table 6.21 that the members has saving in different agencies as in post office, bank, with friends and SHGs before joining SHGs and after joining SHGs. All the amount of savings under different agencies has increased from before to after joining of SHGs but the saving with friends has decreased from ₹ 193.67 to ₹ 105.5. As concern with saving with SHGs the before joining SHGs has showing null value as no amount has saved here but the average annual amount of saving with SHGs after joining SHGs has shown a saving of ₹ 358. The total amount of average annual saving has increased from ₹ 1280.67 to ₹ 1724.042 which states that the members financial economic condition has increased therefore they saving more after joining SHGs.

Paired T-Test for saving in different agencies

For the purpose to know the significant difference of saving in before and after joining SHGs by the members the null hypothesis is framed and which states that "There is no significant difference in the amount of saving among different agencies in before and after joining self help group" and this hypothesis has analysed through the use of Paired T-Test.

The result found by applying Paired T-Test is given in Table-6.22 below:-

Table -6.22
Result of Paired T-Test for saving

Sr. No.	Measures of saving at different agencies	Calculated value of Paired T-Test	Level of significance	Result
1.	Post office	4.017	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level
2.	Banks	-3.457	0.001	Significant at 1% and 5%

				level
3.	Saving with friend	3.146	0.002	Significant at 1% and 5% level
4.	SHGs	-34.221	0.000	Significant at 1% and 5% level

The Paired T-Test has shown the result of average annual amount of saving among different agencies in before and after joining SHGs. The null hypothesis is rejected for all the savings in different agencies and therefore all the different saving agencies showing a significant difference in the saving of members before and after joining the SHGs on all the different level of significance i.e. at 1% and 5% as the level of significance is less than alpha values 0.01 and 0.05.

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